

EFFECT OF MATRIX ALLOY 6061, 7075, A356 ON HOT WORKABILITY OF PARTICLE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The composites with 15vol% of either Al_2O_3 or SiC particles were fabricated by liquid-metal-mixing and DC casting to billets. The specimens were deformed in the ranges 200-500°C and 0.1 to 4 s^{-1} by hot torsion. The flow stress decreased gradually as temperature T rose and strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ declined; in contrast the ductility increased but declined at the highest T. The strength decreased in order 7075, 6061 and A356 in similarity to the bulk alloys but ductility increased in that order. Constitutive analysis showed that a sinh-Arrhenius function fitted well with activation energies much higher than for the matrix alloys and increasing in the title order. The matrix generally exhibited subgrains although compared to the bulk alloy they were smaller and less well formed, so that dynamic recrystallization occurs in high shear regions or near the particle interfaces.

INTRODUCTION

The alloys A356, 6061 and 7075 have been used as matrices for both SiC and Al_2O_3 particulate composites which were produced by Duralcan, San Diego, using liquid metal mixing [1,2]. Since one objective is to mechanically form into secondary products these metal matrix composites (MMC) solidified as billets or slabs for extrusion or rolling [3-5], there has been a broad research program to determine the dependence on temperature T and strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ of the flow stress σ and the ductility ϵ_f [6-22]. Particulate composites are more amenable to deformation processing than short fiber composites because the particles are not so likely to undergo degradation by the deformation; the extent of this is one object of the research. The bulk matrix alloys exhibit better workability at higher T and lower strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ as a result of dynamic recovery (DRV), which normally produces larger subgrain size d and less dense, neater walls [23-27]. The reinforcing particles reduce the workability because of the initial high dislocation density, introduced by their difference in thermal expansivity (ΔCTE) from the matrix and by the constraints to plastic flow arising from their relative rigidity [6,28].

In summary of the project as a whole, the composites have similar strength near 500°C to the matrix alloys but have somewhat reduced ductility. As T falls, the strength of the MMC rises more rapidly than that of the matrix and leads to a higher activation energy in the sinh-Arrhenius constitutive equation [7-21]. The MMC ductilities exhibit maxima between 400 and 500°C and then decrease more rapidly than the respective alloys to become so poor at 200°C as to pose great difficulties in the final stages of rolling or forging [12,22]. The objective here is to emphasize the different composite behaviors resulting from the very different matrix alloys. The A356 is a casting alloy containing 6.5 vol% Si eutectic particles which, depending on size and distribution, cause considerable strengthening but also reduce the ductility particularly below 300°C; it is much less strong and less ductile than the other two alloys [9,10,,13]. The 6061 alloy contains Mg_2Si in

much smaller quantities than the Si eutectic but usually as much smaller particles or partially in solution so that its hot strength is lower and ductility much higher than the A356 [25,29]. The 6061 is generally considered to have very good extrudability while the other two would be considered inferior [3]. The 7075 matrix has much higher precipitate or solute content than the 6061 which gives it higher hot strength and lower hot ductility across the hot working domain and in particular declining workability as T rises above 450°C whereas the 6061 only deteriorates 100°C above that [3,30,31]. The hot working temperatures are much above those for optimum aging so precipitates are usually overaged; however, solute in supersaturation may dynamically precipitate at the beginning of deformation to give an initial peak [25,31]. Commercial extrusions or plate of 6061 and 7075 exhibit elongated grains with some statically recrystallized grains, more frequently as cooling is slower.

EXPERIMENTS

The hot deformation in the ranges 200-500°C and 0.1-4 s⁻¹ was carried out on a hot torsion machine previously described [7,8,18]. Because of the strain gradient from center to surface and in consistency with Von Mises yielding criterion, the following equations were employed for surface strain and related stresses [8,9,17,18]:

$$\epsilon = (r / \sqrt{3}L) (\text{angular rotation}) \quad \sigma = (\sqrt{3} / 2\pi r^3) (\text{torque}) (3+m+n') \quad (1), (2)$$

Table 1: Chemical Compositions (w + %)

Material	Zn	Mg	Cu	Fe	Si	Mn
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /6061	-	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.1
15v%SiC _p /6061	-	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.1
15v%SiC _p /A356	-	0.3	0.2	0.2	7.0	-
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /7075	5.8	2.7	1.3	0.1	0.0	-

Figure 1. Representative flow curves (a) for the 15% particulate composites tested at 1 s⁻¹ and 300°C, 400°C and 500°C.

Figure 2. Optical microscopy of 15%Al₂O₃/7075: a) 300°C, 4 s⁻¹, unetched tangential, particles aligned individually and as groups yet still cellular, some cracks near clusters, x400; b) 250°C, 0.1 s⁻¹, unetched longitudinal, cracks entering from surface touch particles, cellular distribution, x400; c) 500°C, 1 s⁻¹, anodized differential contrast reveals elongated grains, substructure in some grains and some small new grains, particles difficult to distinguish, x400 [A30].

where, r (3.17mm) is gage radius, L (17.5mm) is length, m ($d \log(\text{torque})/d \log \dot{\epsilon}$) corrects for $\dot{\epsilon}$ gradient and n' ($d \sigma/d \epsilon=0$ at the maximum) corrects for ϵ gradient. Some representative stress-strain (σ - ϵ) curves are presented in Figure 1.

The specimens which had been rapidly cooled after straining, were polished mechanically for optical examination in an unetched condition to observe the particles and cracks. The plane of section and the slices for TEM were parallel to the torsion axis and close to the gage surface. The preparation techniques for TEM and SEM-BSI have been described in detail [11-18]. The optical microscopy of unetched 7075 (Figure 2a,b) in similarity to the other MMC, reveals a cellular distribution of angular particles with alignment rising with strain. Cracks are found near the surface and sometimes near clusters. The anodized surface (Figure 2c) is confusing but does exhibit some elongated grains with substructural mottling; there also are small grains much smaller than the particles which can be distinguished by matching with the unetched. Scanning microscopy SEM permits one to distinguish large particles (strongly aligned), bands of precipitates and more strongly deformed zones free of precipitates (Figure 3). Examples of TEM observation (Figure 4) provide some idea of the heterogeneity observed in all the composites. There are regions of subgrains always smaller and more ragged than those in the simple alloy. There are also high dislocation densities in the vicinity of particles; in some cases, these transform into DRX grains [11-16,18-21].

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

As seen in Figure 1, the flow curves at 300°C rise rapidly to a high stress and then decrease fairly rapidly to failure. At 400°C, the maximum stress is not as high and the decrease is more gradual to a higher fracture strain ϵ_f . At 500°C, the stresses are much lower and decline more gradually to a still greater ϵ_f . Such a pattern is true of all the composites except for the 7075 where at 500°C, ϵ_f is very low (0.3 to 0.7) but at 400°C is quite high so that the curves have some similarity to those of the others at 500°C (Figure 1). The strengths at $\dot{\epsilon}=0.1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ are seen to decline smoothly with rising T (Figure 5a) and are consistent with higher values at 1 and 5 s^{-1} (15%SiC/6061 at 300°C is rather low). The strengths of 15%Al₂O₃/6061 which appear lowest of all in Figures 1,5a were somewhat lower than the average values of 10% and 20% Al₂O₃ composites [14,20]. The fracture strain of each composite (Figure 5b) is much less than that of the matrix alloy at 300°C and below. This behavior can generally be explained by the action of the reinforcing particles; their relative rigidity leads to very high interface stresses and the opening of cracks. At higher temperatures, the matrix becomes more ductile so that the stress concentrations are much reduced and the ductility rises more rapidly than that of the matrix.

Examination of fractures on polished tangential or longitudinal sections (Figure 2b) show that the crack always contains many particles but appears to pass through the particle/matrix interface

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of tangential gage sections of A356 illustrating the alignment of a) 12 μm Si particles, matrix dark, x300 and b) coarse Mg₂Si particles (in bright segregated bands) between zones of high strain. The coarse cast alloy is very close to a composite itself x1800 .

with almost no evidence of passing through fractured particles. The cracks appear to mainly connect particles that are fairly uniformly distributed and only occasionally to pass through especially dense clusters of particles [10,13,19,20,22]. The original distribution appears to be somewhat cellular related to the particles being pushed ahead of growing primary dendrites; occasionally the clusters are associated with interdendritic porosities. The sections were studied for fractured particles, especially ahead of cracks; however, none could be absolutely identified. The particles are under compressive stresses due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (ΔCTE) [28]; when that stress is reversed near a crack tip, the interface appears to undergo decohesion. Near the gage surface, particles are frequently aligned in spirals around the torsion axis (Figure 3). The associated matrix shear strain does not seem to have cracked the particles or caused their decohesion even though they are spread further apart and rotated so their long axes follow the alignment. No voids were observed at the particles as after cold rolling of a 1050 Al matrix with SiC particles [6].

The cracks become increasingly irregular at higher T and lower $\dot{\epsilon}$ giving the appearance of dimples [10,19,20]. Fractographic dimples were certainly observed on 25°C bend tests on the 6061/Al₂O₃ specimen shoulders, being better developed at higher annealing temperature in association with higher energy to propagate the crack [22,32]. These tests show that the composite with SiC particles are much less ductile in terms of energy absorbed and in dimple appearance which indicates cracking through fine precipitates which do not initiate dimples except at high T. The presence of fine precipitate particles may serve as matrix constraints which in association with the reinforcements lower ductility much below that of the bulk alloy. The low ductility of 7075 composite and alloy at 500°C (Figure 5b) and above is thought to be related to enlarged particles or possibly melted phases at the GB [30,31]. In the A356 composite the Si particles are much refined compared to the bulk alloy due to Sr modification; the 6.5v% of 6-12µm Si particles in the bulk alloy, which make it behave almost like an MMC, serve as initiation sites that are similarly effective as the 18µm SiC particles in the MMC [10,13]. The 0.1 to 1µm Si particles in the composite seem to have only a minor effect on the crack propagation. In a comparison of powder metallurgy alloys and 20v% SiCp composites by Pickens et al. [33], the ductility of 7090 decreased markedly above 425°C whereas that of 6061 remained high up to 525°C; extrusion had to be limited to 425°C for 7090 despite the high flow stress [33].

For all composites, the dependence of the maximum flow stress σ on $\dot{\epsilon}$ and T is well represented by the following equation (Figures 6,7) [8,9,17,18,23-25,29-31]:

$$A(\sinh \alpha\sigma)^n = \dot{\epsilon} \exp(Q_{HW} / RT) = Z \tag{3}$$

Table 2: Subgrain sizes at 1 s⁻¹ and constitutive constants for some composites

Material	Subgrain Diameter (µm)				Q _{HW} kJ/mol	n	α MPa ⁻¹	Reference
	200	300	400	500°C				
15v%SiC/A356					263	3.2	0.052	9,13
15v%SiC/6061	0.6	1.0	0.9	1.6	233	2.7	0.052	14,18
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /6061					209	2.6	0.052	
10v%Al ₂ O ₃ /6061	-	1.0	2.0	3.0	180	2.8	0.052	14,16
6061	1.4	2.5	3.4	6.0				16
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /7075					292	2.23	0.052	17
7075					227	2.35	0.052	17
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /6061*	1.0	1.4	2.5	4.8	222	5.11	0.03	35
6061*	1.4	2.4	3.7	7.7	204	5.01	0.035	35
15v%Al ₂ O ₃ /7075*	0.7	1.1	1.9	3.8	169	6.7	#	36
7075*	1.1	1.4	2.1	3.3	137	7.3	#	36
7075*	0.6	0.9	1.8	5.0	150	1.9	0.052	30
A356 (6.5%Si _p)	-	0.8	1.9	4.4			0.052	13
Al 1100	1.4	2.0	2.9	4.2*	156	4.0	0.052	26
Al-0.65Fe(dispersoid)	0.7	1.0	2.1	5.6*	270	3.5	0.052	27

* interpolated from Z values # power law

where, $R = 8.31 \text{ J/molK}$ and $\alpha = 0.052 \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ as commonly used for Al alloys. The material constants are A , n the stress exponent and Q_{HW} the activation energy ($\approx 2.3Rns$, s slope of $\log [\sinh \alpha \sigma]$ vs. $[1/T]$). The analysis is illustrated for 15% Al_2O_3 /6061 composite and alloy; the several constant T lines (or constant $\dot{\epsilon}$ lines) in Figure 7a,b are the best fit by linear regression providing slopes n (or s), which contribute to the averages listed in Table 2. The Zener-Hollomon parameter Z combines the two control variables and can draw all data into a single line as illustrated in Figure 7c. For all the materials, the $\sigma - \dot{\epsilon}$ dependence is shown for 400°C in Figure 6a and the Arrhenius $\sigma - T$ relationship is shown in Figure 6b at 1.0 s^{-1} . The values of n (Table 2) fall in the range 2 to 3 without any pattern relative to matrix or particle content. These values cannot be related to the stress exponent in the creep power law, which is about 5 at low $\dot{\epsilon}$ and σ ; at the present stress levels the power law exponent would be greater than 8. Attempts to use the power law on particulate composites have always resulted in a kink in the Arrhenius plot and two Q values [16,18,21,33,34]. The high n values for the A356 composite and bulk alloy result in the highest Q_{HW} values, 311 and 219 kJ/mol respectively. In the Arrhenius plot (Figure 6b), the slopes are highest for the 7075 composite because of the markedly high strength at 300 and 250°C , thus contributing significantly to the high value of Q_{HW} 292 kJ/mol (Table 2). For 6061 composites, the hot strengths and Q_{HW} in the range 209-233 kJ/mol are in agreement with results of Pickens, Tuler and colleagues [7-9,33,34]. The relative behavior of 7075 and 6061 composites with 15v% Al_2O_3 was also observed for 7090 and 6061 composites with 20v% SiCp [33]. The bulk alloys have Q_{HW} in the range 160-220 kJ/mol, which are higher than for commercial purity Al where 150 kJ/mol can be related to vacancy migration and dislocation climb [23-25]. The high values of Q reflect the complexity of the dislocation interactions in the composites, which are influenced by the non-uniform constraints from the rigid particles and the high density of ΔCTE

Figure 5. The variation of maximum σ and ϵ_f with T at $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for A356, 6061 and 7075 MMC with either SiC or Al_2O_3 .

Figure 4. TEM micrographs of tangential gage sections of 15% SiCp/A356: a) 300°C , 0.1 s^{-1} , DRX grain A around a small particle with other grain B, subgrains C, D, $\times 23,500$; b) 400°C , 5.0 s^{-1} , subgrains containing considerable internal dislocation density, $\times 25,500$; c) 500°C , 0.1 s^{-1} , high dislocation density around a small particle, A, DRX grain boundaries B, C; $\times 20,000$.

dislocations, which have formed due to cooling from solidification [28], thus being independent of the deformation conditions. Industrially, higher Q_{HW} indicate more rapid rises in hot strength as T decreases to 300 or 200°C, warning of high finishing forces in forging or rolling [3,4,15].

MICROSTRUCTURAL OBSERVATIONS AND MECHANISMS

TEM examination of all composites with either Al_2O_3 , or SiC revealed that in comparison to the bulk alloys, the dislocation substructures were very inhomogeneous, ranging from uniform distributions to small cells and to subgrains [11-18,20-22] (Figure 4). All these distributions shifted to lower densities as T rose and $\dot{\epsilon}$ fell. While this behaviour had some similarity to the T and $\dot{\epsilon}$ dependence of substructures in bulk alloys, the dislocation distributions were much more inhomogeneous and dense. For the composites, the sizes were measured only in the regions which had the appearance of subgrains; the selective omission of high density regions has a degree of subjectivity. At 400°C, 0.1 s⁻¹, the 6061 alloy had an average size of 3.8 μm, whereas the best recovered group in the 15v% SiC composites had 1.2 μm [14]; at 500°C, 4s⁻¹, the subgrains are 5.6 μm in the alloy and 1.5 μm in the composite. Subgrain sizes for 6061 and 10% Al_2O_3 /6061 are listed in Table 2 along with published results [13,26,27,30,31]. The substructures observed here are much finer and varied than those reported by Chandra and colleagues possibly because of the particle character [35,36]. For any deformation condition, composites with higher particle content have greater strength, dislocation density and heterogeneity [11-16,18-21].

The high dislocation densities are frequently in contact with the particles, since they do not deform and the matrix must undergo additional strain [6]. However, groups of particles set up intense flow patterns, lying between the particles and also accumulating dislocations (Figure 3). In the densest regions, fine cells of 0.1 - 0.2 μm, with misorientations of over 20°, are considered to be about to undergo dynamic recrystallization (DRX) (Figure 4) [11-16,18-21,37]. In other regions, small grains of 0.5 to 2 μm were observed apparently formed by DRX. Because of the evident heterogeneity, DRX did not progress to overrun the entire matrix. One should recall that in DRX, grain growth is stopped by the build up of substructure within the new grains, so that there is insufficient strain energy differential to sustain the migration [37]. There was no evidence of static recrystallization or metadynamic type, (static growth of dynamic nuclei) [37].

A model of the dislocation distributions [15,20] starts from a high, non-uniform density of ΔCTE dislocations formed during cooling from solidification along with a complex distribution of internal stresses [28]. On heating to the deformation T, additional ΔCTE dislocation are generated; being greater for higher T. While being thermally equilibrated at the deformation T, plastic flow relieves the internal stresses and static recovery reduces the density of the substructure more at higher T. During deformation, DRV attempts to develop a substructure consistent with the local

Figure 6. The application of Equation 3 to the data a) variation of σ with $\dot{\epsilon}$ at 400°C and b) Arrhenius-type dependence of σ upon T at 1 s⁻¹.

strain rate conditions, being higher at higher T and lower $\dot{\epsilon}$; moreover, there can be considerable reduction in dislocation density during progress to a steady state strain of 2 [23-27]. For each particle considered separately, there is highly localized flow in the adjacent matrix to make up for the absence of flow in the rigid particle. However, the effect of groups of particles must be considered; there are zones of high plastic flow in addition to the single particle effects. This substructural model is able to explain the high activation energies observed in the composites. At high T, the MMC flow stresses are almost the same as those for the bulk alloy because the DRV mechanisms are able to reduce the dislocation densities to about the same level, despite the non-uniform strain distribution imposed by the rigid particles. As T decreases, the initial dislocation density is higher and more heterogeneous. The strain distribution due to the particles tends to become less uniform because of the higher yield stress and localized T increases in the high shear regions. In comparison to the bulk alloy, it becomes more difficult for the DRV mechanisms to rearrange the dislocations into orderly, low energy arrays in association with annihilations: it is to be emphasized that the rates of the unit mechanisms such as climb are not changed, it is just that they do not accomplish as much. The activation energies of overaged matrix alloys are similar to that for pure Al [23-27,30,31]; however, the stresses are higher, notably at low T, in 6061 and more so in 7075 which may be related to increasing levels of precipitation. In age hardenable Al alloys deformed in the solution treated condition, there are increasing levels of dynamic precipitation as T declines leading to very high dislocation densities and initial stresses [25,29-31]. However as strain progresses, particles coalesce and recovery reduces the initial high dislocation density to develop the same steady state level as material overaged prior to deformation.

CONCLUSION

The composites of A356, 6061 and 7075 with 15vol% Al_2O_3 or SiC exhibit reasonable hot workability with marked decrease in flow stress and increase in ductility, as T increases and $\dot{\epsilon}$ decreases. The sinh-Arrhenius function provides a suitable definition of the behaviour; however, the apparent activation energies of the composites are very high, ranging upward from 230 kJ/mol dependent on the matrix in comparison to the range of 150 to 190 kJ/mol for the bulk matrix alloys. The principal mechanism is dynamic recovery, which is much restricted in the composites by the high density of ΔCTE dislocations at low T and by the constraints to flow exerted by the rigid reinforcing particles. With decreasing temperature, the particles increase the average density and also the heterogeneity to give a range from subgrains to non-cellular arrays. Unlike the bulk alloys, the dislocation densities in the MMC's rise to such levels that dynamic recrystallization nuclei form near the particles or in regions of concentrated strain. The DRX does not spread throughout the composite.

Figure 7. Equation 3 is further illustrated for 15% $Al_2O_3/6061$ MMC: a) constant T lines, b) nearly parallel constant $\dot{\epsilon}$ lines and c) Z organizes data into a single line.

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BEHAVIOUR OF LOW TEMPERATURE MATRIX SYSTEMS
